

**ATTITUDE OF UNDERGRADUATE HAUSA LANGUAGE STUDENTS
TOWARDS THE COURSE IN THE USMANU DANFODIYO UNIVERSITY,
SOKOTO, NIGERIA**

BY

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**BEING A RESEARCH PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF
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CERTIFICATION

This research project by Abu-Ubaida Sani (1210406003) and Ubaida Usman (1210406012) has met the requirements for the award of Bachelor of Arts Education Hausa (B. A. Ed. Hausa) in the Department of Educational Foundations, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto and is therefore approved for its contribution to knowledge.

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DEDICATION

This research project is dedicated to right-doers.

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In the name of Allah the Merciful, the Compassionate: all thanks and praises are due to Him. May His peace, blessings and salutations be upon His beloved prophet Muhammad (S.A.W.), his households, companions and those who follow their path up till the day of judgment.

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ABSTRACT

The research work delves into the attitudes of undergraduate Hausa language students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria. Four research questions are raised for the study. Thus: (1) To what extent are the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto interested in the course? (2) To what extent have the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto attached pride to the course? (3) To what extent does the attitude of the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto has effect on learning the course? (4) To what extent the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto would willingly continue with the study of the course as a life career? However, the objectives of the study focus on finding answers to the research questions. In chapter two of the study, different relevant literatures are consulted and reviewed in order to get a clear picture of the subject matter. The design and instrument employed for the research are discussed in the chapter three, which are descriptive survey and questionnaire respectively. Two sets of questionnaires are framed and administered to teachers and students fittingly. Both the questionnaires are designed in such a way as to provide information relevant to answer the four research questions. In chapter four, the data collected are presented in tabular form and analyzed using simple percentages. Summary of the major findings are made based on the analyses. However, the findings show that; majority of the under graduate Hausa language students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto have good attitudes towards the course, though many of them developed the interest only after been given the course to study. Finally, the study tables some recommendations, among which one is, those concerned should be orienting students at O-levels on how equally all courses are important and prestigious. Another is; those concerned at tertiary institutions level should attach importance to addressing negative attitudes of students towards courses they are admitted to study.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Many researches affirm the role, which students' attitude play in the improvement of their academic achievement (Robert, 1992; Theresa, 2006). Engagements of students to learning are directly molded by the students' attitudinal characteristics toward the learning. These characteristics include motivation, positive learning values, enthusiasm, interest and pride in success among others (Newman, 1992). With these (attitudinal characteristics), a student displays curiosity, a desire to know more as well as positive emotional responses to learning and school in general (Turner 1998; Smerdon 1999; Theresa, 2006).

On the other hand, Adelinda *et al* (2008) conducted an empirical research on the students' attitudes towards learning. The findings show that, to a higher extent, contextual and cultural experiences dictate different kind of attitudes toward school and learning. This is because; social and family experiences influence students' construction of meaning about school and learning. Therefore, it could be concluded at this juncture that, attitudes of learners affect their academic performance. Whereas, on the other hand, attitudes of learners toward learning is as much molded by their cultural experience as well as contextual elements (Theresa, 2006; Adelinda *et al*, 2008).

However, students studying other courses, especially science courses, and sometimes the community at large, positioned Hausa language students at lower elevation. This is for the fact that, Hausa is an indigenous language in Nigeria. Thus, it is regarded as local, common and which has less importance to the political and socio-economic climate of the country. As such, only few are into the study of the course willingly. More so, many

of Hausa students feel ashamed to show out their course of study (Bunza, 2010). This is indeed a great treat against the academic pursuit of the students concerned. Thus, especially considering the relationship which students' attitudes have with learning.

Notwithstanding, if a step is taken towards ascertaining the real causes of this reluctance and lack of pride which Hausa language students treat their course with, a better end could be met. It is therefore of paramount importance to conduct research on this phenomenon, so as to study the attitudes of undergraduate Hausa language students towards the course in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria. The result could be generalized on other Hausa language students studying in various institutions of education other than the location of this research, or serve to open gate for similar and/or further studies.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

It has been proved that the motivation, self-esteem, self-concept and indeed attitudes of a learner, among others, directly or indirectly affect his/her learning outcomes. Learning results from the active involvement of the learner. Meanwhile, the learner's involvement is, to high extent, determined by his/her attitudes towards the course in question.

However, it has been observed that, many undergraduate Hausa Language students did not choose studying it willingly. Thus, they are given the course to study out of volition. More so, many of the students find the course difficult than they expected (i.e. mere language that is used in everyday communication). Perhaps, these could be the

genesis of the low proficiency in both oral and written aspect of the course (Hausa Language).

1.3 Research Questions

The research project is guided by the following research questions:

1. To what extent are the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto interested in the course?
2. To what extent have the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto attached pride to the course?
3. To what extent does the attitude of the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto has effect on learning the course?
4. To what extent the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto would willingly continuo with the study of the course as a life career?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The core objective of this research work is to ascertain the attitudes of undergraduate Hausa language students towards the course in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria.

Nonetheless, it specifically strives to:

1. determine the status of interest, which undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University have in the course,

2. determine the pride which Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto attached to the course,
3. determine the gravity of the effect, which the attitude of Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto has towards learning the course and
4. determine the extent to which the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto would willingly continue with the study of the course as a life career.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The findings of this study are expected to be relevant to the government, educational planners and administrators, parents, language educators and indeed students. The aforementioned categories of beneficiaries will be provided with knowledge of the attitudes of the undergraduate Hausa language students towards the course in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria.

Perhaps, it will provide to the educational planners and administrators, relevant information on the attitudes of undergraduate students towards Hausa language. This could be worthy of consideration during the process of educational planning. More so, guidance and counseling officers could use the findings during ascertaining the causes of failure or success of students. It could as well be useful when sending feedback information to students' parents.

Finally, the findings could serve reference functions to researchers who wish to conduct related researches. This is because, the research highlights on the attitudes of

students towards a language (i.e. Hausa), which could be reason for the failure and impediment of smooth flour of teaching and learning process with respect to the field of study in question.

1.6 Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The research area of coverage is, and limited to determining the attitudes of undergraduate Hausa language students towards the course in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria. This is due to the nature of the study and perhaps a number of factors, which among others include; timeframe, inadequate funds and indeed the academic up-and-comings that must be carried out alongside this research work.

However, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto is selected as the research location. More so, students of the university, precisely undergraduate Hausa language students, formed the research population.

1.7 Operational Definition of Terms

Basic concepts, which this research is concerned about, are deservedly defined as follows:

Interest: means a personal psychological stage, resulting to preference and/or fancy of a certain thing, and thus give it attention without being under command or compulsion from any external force.

Pride: means the psychological feelings of satisfaction, agreeableness, confidence and self-esteem with regard to the person's socio-cultural status, economical status or physical and psychological being.

Attitudes: are the reactions of person towards a particular object(s), event(s) or phenomenon, which includes, beliefs and positive or negative feelings about the attitude object, and which is evaluative in nature.

Life Career: is the path chosen by an individual, which he tries to specialize on and manipulate its cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects in his attempt to earn living and remain an active member of the society.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Introduction

Several researches, at different carders of education, have been conducted on the attitudes of students towards certain aspects of learning, certain courses or the education in general. It is therefore, ideal to revisit such prior works so as to serve as guide to the intended one. Perhaps, and to avoid repetition of already researched problems. As such, this review is conducted under the following headings:

2.2 Conceptual Framework

2.3 Theoretical Framework

2.4 Hausa Language as a Course

2.5 Relationship Between Students' Interest and Learning

2.6 Relationship Between Students' Pride and Learning

2.7 Relationship Between Students' Attitudes and Learning

2.8 Review of Empirical Studies

2.9 Summary and Uniqueness of the Study

2.10 Conclusion

2.2 Conceptual Framework

Chang, (1996) defines interest as an individual's internal orientation when he/she expresses the choice of someone or something. According to Lai (2010), interest in learning is personal preferences with regard to learning, which sometimes means what an individual choose on one thing rather than other things. That, sometimes, resulted to positive psychological state during interaction with circumstances that engenders further learning motives. It is a condition that occurs when someone sees characteristic of situation that is correlated with his/her own need and desire (Sardiman in Firmani, 2009).

However, pride is defined as the feeling of respect that one has for oneself. In other words, it is the feeling of pleasure or satisfaction about something or someone closely connected with the individual concerned (Turnbul, J. *et al* eds, 2015). Tracy & Robins hold that, the feeling of pride might have evolved to provide information about an individual's current level of social status and acceptance (Tracy & Robins, in Isabella & Francesca, 2002). Perhaps, according to Isabella & Francesca, (2002), pride, represented in words like accomplished and confident, is positively associated with personality traits of extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and with genuine self-esteem. Jessica & Richard, (2007) considers pride as an important emotion that plays a critical role in many domains of psychological functioning. It reinforces behaviors such as altruism and adaptive behaviors like achievements. That is to say, pride in a particular discipline is the feeling of confidence, satisfaction, agreeableness and self-esteem of being studying or having been studied the course.

On the other hand, for many years, attitudes had been considered as a central concept of social psychology. Meanwhile, early writers have defined social psychology as the scientific study of attitudes (Norbert & Gerd, 2001). The concept of attitude has been changing over decades. The definitions during the early years were broad compared to the present day's definition of attitude. During the early years, the concept encompassed cognitive, affective, motivational as well as behavioral components. This could be seen if the definitions of the term over the years are tabled. For instance, attitude in 1935 was defined as:

...a mental and neural state of readiness, organized through experience, exerting a directive and dynamic influence upon the individual's response to all objects and situations with which it is related (Allport, 1935: 810).

Similarly, the term is defined by Krech & Crutchfield as:

...an enduring organization of motivational, emotional, perceptual, and cognitive processes with respect to some aspect of the individual's world Krech & Crutchfield (1948: 152).

It could be noted here that, both the definitions above emphasize on the enduring nature of attitudes and their close relationship to individuals' behavior. On the other hand, attitude in the recent years have been regarded as mere concept, which shows likes and dislikes. For instance, in 1999 it is defined as:

...a psychological tendency that is expressed by evaluating a particular entity with some degree of favor or disfavor (Eagly & Chaiken, 1993: 1).

Nevertheless, one thing that is true is that, it is difficult, if not impossible, to design reliable empirical test for attitude evaluation. This is for the fact that, individuals may hold multiple attitudes about an object, a phenomenon or any variable of interest to the

researcher. Thus, an attitude, at a time, would be accessed depending on the time and indeed physical and psychological state of the individual. That is to say, the result will come up with a few credible assumptions, by which each is only well-matched with the available data (Norbert & Gerd, 2001). It is for this reason that Norbert & Gerd, (2001) opine that, attitude and other scientific concepts of its kind are to be evaluated on the basis of their explanatory power, thus, without taking judgmental processes into account.

However, life career is an important phenomenon, which experiences significant shift in its understanding with the global shift in understanding the purpose of education in general. This shift has had implications for ideas about effective career education (Ivan, 2009). Career is defined as series of jobs that a person has in a particular area of work, usually involving more responsibility as time passes (Turnbul, J. *et al* eds, 2015).

2.3 Theoretical Framework

Many theories, over the years, seek to understand how and why individuals change in attitudes (Richardson & Placier, 2001; Michaela, 2002). These theories are referred to as theories of attitudes and many researchers have conducted different works on them (i.e. (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980; Richardson & Placier, 2001; Michaela, 2002).

However, one of such theories of attitude is *Theory of Reasoned Action* (TRA), which suggests that a volitional or voluntary behavior can be predicted directly by individuals' intention to perform the behavior. It predicts that two factors cause behavioral intent, which are attitudes and subjective norms. Thus, individual's behavior is determined by his intention to perform the behavior, and that this intention is, in turn, the function of his attitude towards the behavior and his subjective norms (Michaela, 2002; University of Twente, 2009).

In 1980, Ajzen developed another theory of attitude, notably *Theory of Planned Behavior*. This is for not been satisfied with TRA, which is limited, only, to predicting behaviors over which individuals have will control. In TPB therefore, Ajzen tries to explain that, the extent to which some intentions to act can be carried out depends particularly on the levels of control individuals have over behavior. It links beliefs and behaviors, and thus explains human behavior in relation to behavioral control (Michaela, 2002; University of Twente, 2009).

TPB has the assumptions that, any specific attitude towards the behavior in question is expected to predict that behavior. Also, there is the need to measure individuals' subjective norms when measuring attitude towards a certain behavior (University of Twente, 2009).

However, TPB is concerned with the following beliefs:

- i. *Behavioral Beliefs*: These are beliefs about consequences of the behavior.
- ii. *Normative Beliefs*: These are belief, which concerned normative expectation of others.
- iii. *Control Beliefs*: This type of beliefs are concerned about the presence of factors that may facilitate or impede performance of the behavior (VBM, 2016).

Therefore, in the context of this research, attitudes of undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto might be positive or negative towards the course due to specific individual subjective norms. The Theory of Planned Behavior guides this research work.

2.4 Hausa Language as a Course

Hausa has been taught outside Africa since 1885, when the first course was offered in Berlin, Germany. Today Hausa is taught on a regular basis throughout the world, mainly at universities that have a department specializing in African languages (Ekkehard, 2012; Thompson, 2015; ALS, 2015). More than any other language in Africa, Hausa language has the highest number of specialist, ranging from holders of NCE, Diploma, B.A., M.A. Mphil, Ph. D. and indeed number of professors (Bunza,2015).

However, Nigerian universities that offer Hausa language include; Ahmadu Bello University in Zaria; Bayero University in Kano, Federal University Kashere in Gombe, University of Maiduguri in Maiduguri, Sokoto State University in Sokoto, Ummaru Musa ‘Yar’adua University in Katsina and Usmanu Danfodiyo University in Sokoto among others (Adejala, 2014).

Hausa is also taught, especially in form of linguistics, in countries other than Nigeria. They include African as well as Non-African countries such as: Warsaw University in Poland, University of London in United Kingdom, Research Institute for the Languages and Cultures of Asia and Africa (ILCAA) in Japan, University of South Africa in South Africa and University of Ghana, in Ghana among others (SBA, 2012).

There are various works on Hausa which are made by the non-*Hausawa*. ALS, (2015) outlines some of them thus; German missionary Jakob Friedrich Schon’s *Grammar of the Hausa Language* was published in 1862. His publication opened floor for a number of scholarly works concerning the Hausa language. The early ones among them include; Sergio Baldi’s *Systematic Hausa Bibliography* (1977), Paul Newman’s *The Hausa*

Language: An Encyclopedic Reference Grammar (2000), and Philip J. Jaggar's *Hausa* (2001) (Yahaya, 1988; Atuwo, 2009; ALS, 2015).

2.5 Relationship Between Students' Interest and Learning

Yi-je, (2011) opines that, in a classroom setting, interest is required to meet students' intellectual as well as emotional needs. However, interest can never be imposed on an individual by external forces, but a teacher can help increase the learners' interest. In 2008, Yang studied students from seven countries. The result of his study shows that, those who have both confidence and interest in learning science always showed positive achievements on the area of science. That is simply to say, students with higher levels of interest in science performed better in science, than those with mid and lower level interest (Ye-je, 2011).

2.6 Relationship Between Students' Pride and Learning

Learner's pride on particular discipline of study could positively influence his learning achievements. Siek, Connelly & Rogers (2006) hold that, the pride many individuals have influence their choices, thus resulting in preference interfaces that they could not accurately interpret. In essence, the level of pride a learner has on a course is subject to his interest in that course. Notwithstanding, the pride of learner on a particular discipline would determined his/her attitude towards that discipline. As such, student's pride is a determiner of his/her learning achievements.

2.7 Relationships Between Students' Attitudes and Learning

Numerous literatures justify the relationship between students' attitudes and learning (i.e. Robert, 1992; Theresa, 2006; Ibrahim, 2008; Rasaan, 2011; Tambuwai, 2012). Robert, (1992) believes that, without positive attitudes and perceptions (to learning),

students have little chance of learning proficiently, if at all. This is similar to Theresa's opinion, in which he holds that, extensive evidence exists that engagement and motivation are critical elements in student success and learning (Theresa, 2006).

On the other hand, however, learning achievements have significant influence on students' attitudes towards learning. Students with lower performance and higher rate of school failure have more negative attitudes towards learning and education in broad. That is to say, previous school performances experienced by students have negative influence on the attitudes they show towards learning. Perhaps, they will be less committed to school as well as learning activities (Adelinda, *et al*, 2008).

2.8 Review of Empirical Studies

This section accounts for the previous literatures, which are related to this research project. The purpose is to have a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter of the study, as pointed out by Ogbonna, Dakun & Dewan, (2006). They include Ph. D. Thesis, M. Ed. Dissertation, Research Projects as well as books and journals. Below is a review of the related empirical studies:

Enyia, (1975) conducted a research entitled: "Higher education in Nigeria from the earliest times to 1972." In the research, Enyia accounts for the developmental history and some challenges of the early higher education in Nigeria. This includes, students, teachers, government and parents' attitudes towards the education. Therefore, for the aforementioned phenomina, which Enyi discusses in his work, it (his work) is related to this research project. However, they have dissimilarities in the sense that, Enyia is concerned with the accounts of higher education in Nigeria from the earliest time to 1972, whereas this

research work deals with the attitude of undergraduate Hausa language students towards the course in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria. Thus, they differ in terms of location and populations of the studies.

Akporere, (1987) conducted a research on: “Attitude of Sokoto state students towards science.” In the research, Akporere investigates into the manner by which Sokoto state students conceive and are motivated towards sciences. His study is related to this research in terms of the variable (i.e. attitude). However, the two differ in their populations of the study and location. Akporere is concerned with secondary school students, while this research projects deals with undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto.

Bala, (1987) conducted a research entitled: “The attitude of students towards Islamic studies as a discipline in post primary institutions: A case study of some selected secondary schools in Anchau-Zone, Kaduna state.” Bala’s work and this research are having close relationship, because both investigate into the attitudes of students towards certain courses of study (i.e. Islamic Studies and Hausa Language respectively). However, the two differ in terms of location, population of the study as well as the subjects in question.

Haruna, (1994) conducted a research entitled: “Attitudes of students towards Geography in Nigerian Universities: A case study of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto.” However, the research investigates on the attitudes of the students (that constitutes the research population), towards geography as a course of study. This research and his own are related. This is because, both the researches aimed at studying students’

attitudes towards courses (Hausa and Geography respectively). They are also related in terms of location of the studies. Notwithstanding, they differ in the sense that Haruna is concerned with the attitudes of students towards Geography, while this research looks into the attitudes of undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University towards the course.

Richard, (1995) investigates into, “The attitude of female students towards the study of Geography.” He tries to show the conception, feelings and motivation of female students towards geography as a course. However, investigation on attitudes of students towards courses is the linking element between this research and that of Richard. Nonetheless, they differ in terms of location and courses in question.

Muhammad, (1997) conducted a research entitled: “A survey of the attitude of students towards technical and vocational education in Sokoto State.” In the research, Muhammad studies the manner with which students conceived and/or get motivated (being it positively or negatively) towards technical and vocational education. This research and Muhammad’s are related for the fact that, they both study attitudes of students towards fields of study. However, they have dissimilarities as technical and vocational educations deals mainly with the affective domain of knowledge, whereas, Hausa language as a course is more of cognitive aspect of knowledge.

Nweke, (2000) conducted a research entitled: “The attitude of female towards western education in Koko, Kebbe local government area.” In the research, Nweke studies the attitude of females towards education (formal education) in general. This research and Nweke’s are related in the sense that, they both study students’ attitudes towards education.

Nevertheless, they differ in some ramifications such as, research location and the target populations of the studies.

Tambuwal, (2001) conducted a research entitled: “Relationship among self-concept, self-other motivation and career maturity of teachers in tertiary institution in Sokoto state.” In the research, Tambuwal tries to show how related are self-concept and self-other motivation on one hand, and career maturity of teacher (i.e. teachers of tertiary institutions in Sokoto), on the other. His study and this research work are related as they both deal with attitudes towards educational phenomena (i.e. career maturity and Hausa language as a course respectively). Nevertheless, they differ in terms of population of the study, location of the study as well as variables.

Daura, (2004) wrote on: “The attitude of female students towards mathematics: A case study of selected girls secondary schools in Sokoto State.” The research presents the attitudes of females - constituting the research population - towards mathematics. It is similar to this research in terms of the concern on attitudes of students towards certain courses. However, they differ in some ramifications. Secondary school students constitute Daura’s population of the study, while university students formed the population of the study of this research. More so, the courses in question differ.

Ibrahim, (2008) conducted a research entitled: “Study of relationship between senior secondary school students’ attitudes and academic achievements in Physics.” The research shows how students’ achievement in physics is related to their attitudes. However, the findings of the research affirm that, attitudes of students have significant influence on their academic performance. Ibrahims’s work is related to this research topic. This is because;

they both are concerned with students' attitudes towards certain courses. Nevertheless, they differ in terms of population of the study, location as well as subject of consideration.

Bello, (2010) wrote on; "A study of science education students attitudes and utilization of information communication technologies in Federal University of Technology, Minna." In the study, he looks into the manner with which students of Federal University of Technology, Minna conceive, are motivated for or against, and utilize information communication technologies provided to them. Bello's study and this research work are related, for both the two are concerned with students' attitudes in educational palaver. Yet, they differ in the sense that, Bello study students' attitudes towards information communication technology, while this research is concerned with the attitudes of undergraduate Hausa language students towards the course in Usmanu Danfodiyo University.

Rasaq, (2011) wrote on: "Relationships among students' study habits, achievements, motivation, self-other motivation and academic performance in tertiary institutions in Kwara state." Perhaps, habits and motivation are aspects of attitude. Therefore, Rasaq study is related to this research work in terms of investigation on students' attitudes towards academic palaver. However, they differ in some ramifications. In his study, he investigates into the relationships between students study habits, achievements motivation, self-other motivation and academic performance, whereas, this research work is interested in studying the attitudes of undergraduate Hausa language students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University towards the course. Thus, they differ in terms of population of the study, location of the study as well as variables in consideration.

Tambuwal, (2012) conducted a research entitled: “Locus of control and attitude to school as correlates of academic performance of secondary school students of Sokoto state.” In the research, Tambuwal shows that, locus of control and attitudes of students have great impact on their academic performances. He states that, locus of control could be internal or external. It is internal if an individual (i.e. the student) believes to have influence on events and their outcomes. On the other hand, locus of control is said to be external if the individual concern (i.e. student) believes external forces are of total control of events and their outcomes. Tambuwal’s work and this research project are related in aspects like variables (i.e. attitude). However, the two differ with regard to population of the studies and location.

Badau, (2014) wrote on “Factors influencing students’ choice of tertiary education programs in Nigeria.” In the paper, he concludes that, certain factors affect the attitudes of students towards courses and tertiary institutions. Thus, some factors motivate students to select a certain course or apply to study in certain tertiary institutions. These factors includes; parents, school councilors, mass media and friends. Badau’s work is related to this research project in the sense that, his work points some factors, which result to positive attitudes of students towards a particular course or tertiary institution. Nonetheless, they differ in some ramifications. Badau’s work studies the factors that influence students’ choice of tertiary education programs, whereas, this research project is aimed at studying the attitudes of undergraduate Hausa language students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria towards the course.

However, other empirical studies conducted, which are related to this research include: “Attitude of students towards overcrowded classroom: Study of some selected

secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis,” (Kwaifa, 2008); “A study of pupils attitudes towards science in some selected secondary schools in Ilorin local government area of Kwara states,” (Nagari, 1985); “The perception of students of Faculty of Education and Extension Services Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto to teaching profession,” (Ibrahim, 2004); “A study of students attitudes towards science in some selected schools in Gusau metropolis Zamfara state,” (Kabiru, 2012); “Attitude of primary school pupils towards language acquisition and learning: A case study of Sokoto metropolis,” (Umar, 2005); “An investigation into some factors that determine students’ negative attitudes towards mathematics in Sokoto metropolis,” (Isa, 2002) and “The attitude of students towards the effect of global warming on school adjustment: A case study of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto,” (Usman, 2010); “Perception of students’ difficult topics in senior secondary mathematic curriculum in Sokoto state,” (Isiaka, 2009); “Attitude to academic subjects, locus of control and academic achievements among senior secondary schools students in Sokoto state,” (Bakori, 2009) and “Hausa language as a mode of physics instruction; its effect on students’ achievement in Kebbi state,” (2009); “Divergent thinking: Its relationship with convergent thinking and academic achievement of a sample of Nigerian school students in Sokoto,” (Sulaiman, 1984); “Perception of teachers student attitudes towards academic work in selected secondary schools of Sokoto,” (Garba, 1984) and “Relationship between attention deficit hyperactivity, personality and academic performance among primary school pupils in Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara states,” (Njoku, 2009) among others.

2.9 Summary and Uniqueness of the Study

At this juncture, it is worthy to note that, this research project is unique. Perhaps, the work is unique in its own way, in terms of research design, population of the study, sample size, location of the study as well as instrumentation and methodology of data collection. The research employed two sets of questionnaires in order to have responses capable of answering the research questions. The location of this study is Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. More so, the population of the study consists of all undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, which formed the total number of one hundred and ninety eight (198) students. Perhaps, and Hausa lecturers of the Department of Nigerian Languages, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, which have a total number of twenty-six (26) lecturers.

However, the sample size of this study comprises of fifty-nine (59) students (which is the 30% of the population, i.e. 198), and thirteen (13) lecturers (which is 50% of their population, i.e. 26). Considering the sample size and empirically validated instrument (questionnaire) to be used for this study (Attitudes of Hausa Language Students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria), the findings of this research could be generalized to similar situations and/or academic environments.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This research work is guided by certain methodologies. Thus, research design, population of the study, sample and sampling techniques, instrumentation and indeed the method of data collection and analysis. This chapter deals with the aforementioned research methods and procedures.

3.2 Research Design

The research design employed for this study is descriptive research. Descriptive form of survey studies, investigates the present situation of attitude and it describes a given state of affairs as carefully as possible (Frankel & Wallen, in Inuwa, 2008). However, Nwana, (2007) refers to descriptive research as the best method of research as it includes the use of questionnaire or interviews for data collection. This research used questionnaires to obtain the needed data for the study. Perhaps, percentage are calculated and the data obtained are analyzed in order to identify the strength of the responses made to the questions.

3.3 Population of the Study

Population of the study is the limit within which research finding(s) is/are applicable (Habibu, *et al*, 2014). The population of this study comprises of all undergraduate Hausa Language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. Thus, consisting of four levels (100L to 400L), which all in all amount to one hundred and ninety

eight (198) students. The population distribution according to levels of the students is presented below:

Table 1: Population of Undergraduate Hausa Language Student of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, 2015/2016 Session

Level	Males	Females	Total
100L	21	3	24
200L	17	2	19
300L	53	4	59
400L	81	15	96
Total			198

Source: UDUS Web Team, (2014)

However, the population of the study also include Hausa lecturers in the Department of Nigerian Language, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. They are twenty-nine in number, and the table below shows their population according to their respective areas of specializations:

Table 2: Population of Hausa Language Lecturers of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, 2015/2016 Session

Specialization	Population
Culture	7
Language	7
Linguistics	2
Literature	10
Total	26

Source: Department of Nigerian Languages, (2016)

3.4 Sample and Sampling Techniques

Sampling is described by Ketkesone, (2009:3) as: "... the selection of number of study units from a define study population." Ndagi in Ladan & Yakubu (2015) describes a sample as a listed number of elements selected from a population as a representation of the population. However, a sample of seventy-five (59) students, which is the thirty percent (30%) of the target population, is used to represent the one hundred and ninety eight (198) undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. This process is justified by Nwana, (2007) who opines that:

However, there are certain non definite practice among social research workers that the beginners can adopt... if few thousands, a 10% sample will do." (Nwana in Ladan & Yakubu, 2015:22).

Notwithstanding, questionnaires are allocated to randomly selected students in each level in order to have an adequate basis of generalization.

On the other hand, a set of questionnaires are designed to be administered to Hausa lectures in Department of Nigerian Languages, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria. The total number of the lecturers is twenty-nine (26). Fifty percent (50%) of this population (13) are administered with questionnaires. However, the questionnaires contain questions, which responded as yes, no or undecided, thus, providing relevant data for the research questions. The responses of the lecturers provide an avenue for generalization of the findings. Therefore, the total sampled population (of both teachers and students), is seventy-two (72). The table below illustrates the above statement:

Table 3: Population Sample

S/N	Level	Number of Lecturers	Number Selected	Number of Students	Number Selected
1.	100L	7	4	24	7
2.	200L	7	4	19	6
3.	300L	2	1	29	17
4.	400L	10	5	96	29
Total		26	14	198	59 → 73

Source: UDUS Web Team, (2014); Department of Nigerian Languages, (2016)

3.5 Instrumentation

Research instruments are described by Godfred, (2016: 1) as: “The fact-finding strategies.” or “The tools for data collection.” Two sets of questionnaires are used as the research instrument for data collection. Provisions are made to the respondents to choose from amongst yes, no or undecided by simply ticking on any. Thereafter, their opinions are expressed in form of data, which is relevant and subject to further manipulations. The questionnaires are designed in such a way that, items of information required from the respondents are minimal, to enable them promptly fill and return them accordingly. Each set of the questionnaires contain twenty-three (23) questions, which are responded (both by teachers and students respectively) as yes, no or undecided.

3.5.1 Validity of the Instruments

It is imperative that the data and the instruments of any research to be validated (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2003; Mohammad, 2013). Therefore, expert (i.e. supervisor) has

examined the instrument that is used during this research. Perhaps, he has declared it reliable of maintaining measurement consistency of a test. His suggestions and corrections are carefully studied and implemented in the respective relevant areas.

3.5.2 Pilot Testing

The research has conducted a pilot testing to ascertain validity and reliability of the instrument. The testing is done by randomly selecting forty (40) students, (5 from each level). The instrument was administered to them. Moreover, interval of one week was given from the first administration, after which the same instrument was used for the second administration with the same students. The results obtained during the pilot testing ensured the validity and reliability of the instrument used.

3.5.3 Reliability of the Instruments

Reliability is used to evaluate the stability of measures administered at different times to the same individuals or using the same standard (Corole & Almut, 2008). Measure of stability – otherwise known as test-retest method – is employed in order to determine the uniformity of the measurements during the test administered to the randomly selected students as pilot testing. The results obtained from the first and second administration of questionnaires have measured with reasonable consistency.

3.6 Method of Data Collection

The method employed for data collection is the use of questionnaires. Two sets of questionnaires are formed, in which each contains twenty-three (23) questions. First set of the questionnaires is administered to Hausa lecturers of the Department of Nigerian

Languages, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria; while the other one goes to undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. The questionnaires are designed in such a way as to provide answers to the research questions raised from the problem of the study.

However, in each of the two set of questionnaires, number of questions are technically formed in such a way as to attempt answering a specific question (i.e. one from amongst the four research questions). This is to make the data analysis easier and with higher accuracy anticipation.

3.7 Method of Data Analysis

The method to be employed for the data analysis is techniques of descriptive statistics. This is a process whereby the researcher uses frequency count, simple percentage and tables. The frequency count is used in sorting out the number of responses made to each item of the instrument used for the collection of data (i.e. questionnaires). However, the simple percentages are used to analyze the data obtained from the respondents. Thus, using the formula; $F/T \times 100$, where F stands for frequency of a particular response and T for total responses. Therefore, it is used to describe the magnitude of a particular response to an item in order to show the frequencies and percentages fittingly.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Introduction

This chapter contains the analysis of the data obtained from the field. It deals with the interpretation of the research findings, which are presented in a tabular form. The analysis is molded, accordingly, in such a way as to meet the objectives of the research. However, the presentation and analysis are formed in a way to provide answers to the research questions, which guide the research towards achieving the anticipated objectives. Figures and percentages are employed to convey the information clearly at a glance.

4.2 The First Research Question

RQ 1: To what extent are the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto interested in the course?

The answer to this research question is presented below in a tabular form (i.e. table 4):

Table 4: Students' interest in learning Hausa language

S/N	Item Statement (Students & Teachers)	Yes	No	Undecided
1.	Majority of Hausa language students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto applied to study the course willingly.	84%	16%	0%
2	The students were interested in Hausa language during their O-levels education.	70%	22%	8%
3	The bad attitudes of the students towards the course is negatively affecting their educational achievements.	70%	27%	3%
4	The students will like their children and/or younger Brothers to study the course.	70%	30%	0%
5	The students drive pleasure in participating in studying literatures/works on Hausa?	74%	26%	0%
6	The students buy and/or study Hausa books, which are not part of their curriculum?	89%	10%	1%
7	The students follow Hausa programs on the various media available?	85%	15%	0%

Item 1 in table 4 indicates that, 84% of the participants agreed that, majority of Undergraduate Hausa language students in the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto applied to study the course willingly. However, item 2 in table 4 shows that, 70% of the participants believe that, majority of undergraduate Hausa language students in the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto were interested in Hausa language during their O-levels education. Furthermore, item 3 in table 4 indicates that, majority of the participants (70%) agreed that, the bad attitudes of undergraduate Hausa language students in the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto towards the course is negatively affecting their educational achievements. Moreover, item 4 in table 4 indicates that, 70% of the participants believe, majority of undergraduate Hausa language students will like their children and/or younger

brothers to study the course. More so, according to item 5 in table 4, majority of the participants (74%) believes that, the leading number of undergraduate Hausa language students in the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto drive pleasure in participating in studying literatures/works on Hausa. In addition, item 6 on table 4 indicates that, 89% of the participants believe, majority of undergraduate Hausa language students in the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto buy and/or study Hausa books, which are not part of their curriculum. Lastly, item 7 in table 4 shows that, majority of the participants (85%) believes that, significant number of the students follows Hausa programs on the various media available.

4.3 The Second Research Question

RQ 2: To what extent have the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto attached pride to the course?

The answer to this research question is presented below in a tabular form (i.e. table 5):

Table 5: Students' pride in learning Hausa language

S/N	Item Statement (Students & Teachers)	Yes	No	Undecided
1	The students are proud of Hausa language as their course of study:	68%	14%	0%
2	The students disclose their course of study to their colleagues who study other courses rather than Hausa.	56%	44%	0%
3	The students consider other courses much honorable than their own.	21%	78%	1%
4	The students consider teachers/lecturers of other courses much honorable than teachers/lecturers of Hausa language.	15%	85%	0%
5	The students have been bold enough to stand for and/or depend Hausa language as a course whenever it is challenged.	84%	15%	1%
6	The students would like to be named after their course, (i.e. Malam Hausa, Bahaushe, DanHausa etc).	71%	18%	11%
7	The students have been advising others to study Hausa language.	74%	18%	8%

Item 1 in table 5 shows that 68% of the participants believes that, majority of the undergraduate Hausa language students in the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto are proud of Hausa language as their course of study. However, item 2 in table 5 illustrates that, 56% of the participants believes that, majority of undergraduate Hausa language students in the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto disclose their course of study to their colleagues who study other courses rather than Hausa. Contrarily, item 3 in table 5 indicates that, 78% of the participants believe that majority of the undergraduate Hausa language students do not consider other courses worthy of study rather than their own. Furthermore, item 4 in table 5 indicates that, 85% of the participants believes that, principal number of undergraduate Hausa language students in the Usmanu Danfodiyo University do

not consider teachers/lecturers of other courses much honorable than teachers/lecturers of Hausa language. Moreover, item 5 in table 5 shows that, 84% of the participants believe that, majority of undergraduate Hausa language students in the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto have been bold enough to stand for and/or depend Hausa language as a course whenever it is challenged. More so, item 6 in table 5 illustrates that, leading number of the Hausa language students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto would like to be named after their course, (i.e. Malam Hausa, Bahaushe, DanHausa etc). In addition, item 7 in table 5 indicates that, 74% of the participants believe that, majority of undergraduate Hausa language students of the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto are advising others to study Hausa language.

4.4 The Third Research Question

RQ 3: To what extent does the attitude of the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto has effect on learning the course?

The answer to this research question is presented below in a tabular form (i.e. table 6):

Table 6: Students' attitudes in learning Hausa language

S/N	Item Statement (Students & Teachers)	Yes	No	Undecided
1	The students enjoy the nature of Hausa language as their course of study?	80%	19%	1%
2	The students were happy (specifically about the course) when they got the admission to study Hausa language?	72%	25%	3%
3	The students' lack of interest on some educational activities is subject to the nature and status of the course.	56%	25%	19%
4	The students participate fully, and willingly, in all continuous assessments of the course.	88%	12%	0%
5	The students attend conferences, seminars and public lectures on Hausa language.	68%	32%	0%

Item 1 in table 6 shows that, 80% of the participants believes that, majority of undergraduate Hausa language students in the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto enjoy the nature of Hausa language as their course of study. However, item 2 in table 6 illustrates that, 72% of the participants believes that, majority of the undergraduate Hausa language students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto were happy (specifically about the course) when they got the admission to study Hausa language. Contrarily, item 3 in table 6 indicates that, 56% of the participants believe that, the undergraduate Hausa language students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto lack interest on some educational activities subject to the nature and status of the course. Nonetheless, item 4 in table 6 shows that, 88% of the participants believe that, the undergraduate Hausa language students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto participate fully, and willingly, in all continuous assessments of the course. Finally, item 5 in table 6 illustrates that, 68% of the participants

believe that, the undergraduate Hausa language students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto attend conferences, seminars and public lectures on the course.

4.5 The Fourth Research Question

RQ 4: To what extent the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto would willingly continue with the study of the course as a life career?

The answer to this research question is presented below in a tabular form (i.e. table 7):

Table 7: Students' Preference of Hausa Language as a Life Career

S/N	Item Statement (Students & Teachers)	Yes	No	Undecided
1	The students will like to further their education on Hausa language after the first degree.	73%	15%	12%
2	Under normal circumstance (i.e. favorable salary), the students will like to teach Hausa language as their career.	85%	10%	4%
3	The students have vision towards the development of the language.	78%	22%	0%
4	The students are attempting to enrich Hausa literature by writing books for publication.	73%	19%	8%

Item 1 in table 7 shows that, 73% of the participants believe that, majority of undergraduate Hausa language students in the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto will like to further their education on Hausa language after the first degree. However, item 2 in table 7 illustrates that, 85% of the participants believe that, under normal circumstance (i.e. favorable salary), the undergraduate Hausa language students in the Usmanu Danfodiyo University will like to teach Hausa language as their career. Moreover, item 3 in table 7 indicates that, 78% of the participants believe that, majority of the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto have vision towards the

development of the language. Finally, item 4 in table 7 shows that, 73% of the participants believe that, the undergraduate Hausa language students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto are attempting to enrich Hausa literature by writing books for publication.

4.6 Summary of the Major Findings

The major findings of this research are summarized and presented below:

1. To a highly significant extent, the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto are interested in the course. Yet, majority developed the interest only after they are given the course to study.
2. The undergraduate Hausa language students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto have, to high extent, attached pride to the course.
3. The undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto barely have negative attitude towards the course, which have effect on their educational achievements.
4. Majority of the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto would willingly like to continue with the study of the course as a life career.

4.7 Discussion of the Research Findings

According to the data obtained during this research, majority of the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (80%) applied to study the course willingly. Notwithstanding, during the research, the researchers learnt that these responses are contrary to the reality. That is to say, majority of the undergraduate Hausa

language students of the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto are given the course out of their will rather than applying to study it willingly (as the data claim). By interaction with some of the students, the researchers learnt that, the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto developed interest in the course only after been admitted. Thus, to a high extent that they wished they had applied for it initially.

However, this interest, which the students developed towards the course after been given the admission to study it, make majority of them to have good attitudes towards the course. Yet, about 70% of the participants agreed that, from amongst the students, those with bad attitudes towards the course are affected negatively in terms of academic achievements. This justifies the opinion of Robert, (1992) where he opines that, without positive attitudes to learning, students have little chance of learning proficiency. In addition, about seventy percent (70%) of the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto will like their children and/or younger brothers to study the course. It is also due to the interest they have in the course, they buy and/or study Hausa literary works, which are not even part of their curriculum as well as follow Hausa programs on various media available.

Moreover, the research indicates that, the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto have attached a great pride to the course. Here, the researchers also learnt that, the development of this pride comes up only after finding themselves in the system. With this, about 56% of the students disclose their course to those studying other courses. Also, irrespective of the way Hausa language (as a course) is positioned by the society at lower elevation (Bunza, 2015), about 82% of the students do not consider their course or lecturers inferior to other courses or the lecturers of other

courses. For that however, about 84% of them have been bold to depend the course whenever it is challenged. This indicates how proud the students really are of the course. In addition, about 74% of them do advice others to study the course. More so, about 71% of them are ready to be named after the course.

Furthermore, though majority of the students had bad attitudes towards the course initially, they later on (majority of them) developed good attitudes towards it. Thus, about 80% enjoy the nature of the course and about 72% were happy about the course after they were admitted to study it. This is an indication that, the teaching and learning activities with regard to the course is, to some extent, planned suitably to arise students' interest. This include, simplifying –systematically – the content, employing suitable method of instruction. However, the nature of a given course also determines the attitudes of students towards same. If the nature is not fittingly suitable to the learners, there is every tendency of them having negative attitudes towards it. According to the findings of this research however, about 56% of undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto are comfortable with the nature of the course, while 19% of the students are indecisive on that. That is to say, only about 25% of the students are not comfortable with the nature of the course.

In addition, students' participation in teaching and learning activities of a particular course defines their attitudes towards it. That is to say, if the students have negative attitudes towards a course, he/she will undeniably remain inactive in the teaching and learning activities of the course. Here, about 88% of the students participate actively in all continues assessments of the course and as well (majority i.e. about 68%) attend conferences, seminars and public lectures on Hausa language. However, the initial bad

attitudes, which the students held towards the course, might be subject to certain variables. Perhaps, factors such as lack of orientation about the course and its status in the society.

Moreover, the data obtained by this research show that, majority of the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto have the will to maintain Hausa language as a life career. Thus, about 73% of them will like to further their education on Hausa after the first degree, while about 12% are indecisive on this. This is to say; only about 15% of them are not willing to further their education on Hausa language. Similarly, about 85% of them will, under favorable salary, like to teach Hausa language as their life career. Finally, about 78% of the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto have vision towards the development of the language and about 73% have been attempting to enrich its literature by writing books for publications. It is clear from the findings above therefore, the students (majority) have held Hausa language with a high esteem and as a life career.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter contains the winding up discussions of the research. It presents the summary of the study, conclusion, recommendations, implication of the study for language educators and indeed suggestion for further studies.

5.2 Summary of the Study

This study is entitled: Attitude of undergraduate Hausa language students towards the course in the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria. The first chapter of the research is the introductory part, which comprises of; the background to the study, the statement of the problem, research questions, objective of the study, significance of the study, scope and limitation of the study and indeed operational definition of terms.

However, chapter two focuses on reviewing literatures related to the study. The chapter consists of the conceptual and theoretical frameworks, discussion of Hausa language as a course, relationship between the central terms of the research (i.e. interest, pride, and attitudes) and learning, review of empirical studies relevant to the research and lastly, the summary and uniqueness of the study.

Moreover, chapter three of this study explains the research design employed for the study, which is descriptive survey. The chapter also presents the population of the study, sample and sampling techniques, instrumentation, method of data collection and indeed the method of data analyses. More so, chapter four of this research work accounts for the

responses of the participants to the instrument (i.e. questionnaire) administered to them. The chapter also contains the analysis of such responses, summary of the major finding and indeed the discussion of the major findings.

Finally, this part of the work (chapter five) consists of the brief highlight of all the chapters of the study. It also carries conclusion and presents some recommendations based on the findings of the research, implication of the research to language educators and suggestions for further studies. Finally, references and appendixes follow.

5.3 Conclusion

Majority of the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto do not like to be identified as part of those who are given the course to study out of their will initially. This is indeed due to interest the developed in the course after being in the system. Therefore, they developed good attitudes towards the course and attached great pride to it. Moreover, majority of them will be willing to hold it as a life career.

5.4 Recommendations

In line with the findings and conclusion of this research, the following recommendations are made:

1. Since the Hausa language students develop interest in the course mostly after been given the course to study, teachers, school authorities and others concerned should orient students at O-levels on how equally all courses are important and prestigious.

This will help the students to choose courses of study not based on the choices of the majority or friends, rather, based on potentialities bestowed in each student.

2. The pride, which the students attached to the course, could be maintained through lecturers' motivation (i.e. motivating the students). Great importance should be attached to the students' pride for its impact on their learning achievements.
3. Lecturers, school management and others concerned at tertiary institutions level should attach importance to addressing negative attitudes of students towards courses they are admitted to study. This could be in form of orientations, public lectures, career talks and positive motivation by lecturers among others.
4. There should be seminars and public lectures, among other ways, to guiding the students on how best they could utilize their course as a life career. This might include the spelling out of its job opportunities.

5.5 Implication of the Study for Language Educators

The findings of this research project, among others, reveal the attitudes of the undergraduate Hausa language students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria towards the course. The findings therefore, are helpful to language educators in certain ramifications. Among them is for the language educators to pay attention on orienting students on how important is it studying a language. Perhaps, it is by studying the indigenous languages that they (the indigenous languages) could be enriched in their various domains of national life such as education, hospitals, market places, National Assembly and States House of Assemblies. Perhaps, this could be as prior campaigns for the development of the indigenous languages. Thus, in order to put an end to what Banjo in

Tsaure & Sani (2016) describes as the silent approval and tacit adoption of English as the national or official language by the federal government of Nigeria.

More so, Hausa language teachers and lecturers should also be committed and devoted to their services. Thus, they should possess the mastery of the subject matter, good teacher-students relation and other characteristics that will motivate students to study the course as well as develop good attitude towards it.

5.6 Suggestion for Further Studies

Based on the findings of this research, the following areas are suggested for further studies:

1. From bad to good: An investigation into the causes of sudden change of attitudes by students studying Hausa language towards the course.
2. Global growing power of Hausa language and the motivation among its students.
3. The status of Hausa language in the eyes of the humanity.
4. What the course 'Hausa Language' is to students studying other courses.

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Questionnaire

Questionnaire 1: Students' Questionnaire

STUDENTS' QUESTIONNAIRE

PLEASE SUPPLY THE FOLLOWING INFORMATION

SECTION A: BIOGRAPHY

i. Level: 100L [], 200L [], 300L [], 400L []

ii. Sex: Male [], Female []

iii. Age:

a. 15 – 20 years []

b. 21 – 25 years []

c. 26 – 30 years []

d. 31 years and above []

iv. Date.....

SECTION B: STRUCTURED QUESTIONNAIRE

(Please tick [✓] appropriately, i.e. Yes, No or Undecided)

Questions

S/N	Items Statement	Yes	No	Undecided
	A: Students' interest in learning Hausa language			
1	Did you willingly apply to study Hausa language as a course?			
2	Were you interested in Hausa language during your O-levels education?			
3	Do you think you would have been performing better if you			

	study another course other than Hausa language?			
4	Would you like your children and/or younger brothers/sisters to study the course?			
5	Do you derive pleasure in participating in studying literatures/works on Hausa?			
6	Do you buy and/or study Hausa books, which are not part of your curriculum?			
7	Do you follow Hausa programs on the various media available?			
	B: Students' pride in learning Hausa language			
8	Are you proud of being a Hausa language student?			
9	Do you normally disclose your course of study to students studying other courses?			
10	Do you consider other courses much honorable than yours?			
11	Do you consider teachers/lecturers of other courses much honorable than teachers/lecturers of Hausa language?			
12	Have you been bold enough to stand for and/or defend Hausa language as a course whenever it is challenged?			
13	Would you like to be named after your course, (i.e. Malam Hausa, Bahausha, DanHausa etc)?			
14	Have you been advising others to study Hausa language?			
	C: Students' attitudes towards learning Hausa language			
15	Do you enjoy the nature of Hausa language as your course of study?			
16	Were you happy (specifically about the course) when you got the admission to study Hausa language?			
17	Do you think your lack of interest on some educational activities is subject to the nature and status of the course?			

18	Do you participate fully, and willingly, in all continuous assessments of Hausa language?			
19	Do you attend conferences, seminars or public lectures on Hausa language?			
	D: Students' Preference of Hausa Language as Life Career			
20	Will you further your education on Hausa after the first degree?			
21	Under normal circumstance (i.e. favorable salary), will you like to have to teach Hausa language as your career?			
22	Do you have vision towards the development of Hausa language education?			
23	Are you attempting to enrich Hausa literature by writing books for publication?			

Questionnaire 2: Lecturers' Questionnaire

LECTURERS' QUESTIONNAIRE

PLEASE SUPPLY THE FOLLOWING INFORMATION

SECTION A: BIOGRAPHY

- i. Area of specialization: Culture [], Language [], Linguistics [], Literature []
- ii. Length of working experience
 - a. 1 – 5 years []
 - b. 6 – 10 years []
 - c. 11 – 20 years []
 - d. 20 years and above []
- iii. Sex: Male: [], Female: []
- iv. Professional qualification/status B.A./B.A. Ed [], M.A. [], Ph. D. []. Professor []
- v. Date.....

SECTION B: STRUCTURED QUESTIONNAIRE

(Please tick [✓] appropriately, i.e. Yes, No or Undecided)

Questions

S/N	Items Statement	Yes	No	Undecided
	A: Students' interest in learning Hausa language			
1	Do majority of Hausa language students applied to study the course willingly?			
2	Do you think the Hausa language students were interested in the course during their O-level education?			
3	Do you think the attitude of the students towards the course is affecting their educational achievements?			
4	Do you think the students would like their children and/or younger brothers/sisters to study the course?			

5	Do you think the students get pleasure in participating in studying literatures/works on Hausa?			
6	Do the student buy and/or study Hausa books, which are not part of the curriculum?			
7	Do the students follow Hausa programs on the various media available?			
	B: Students' pride in learning Hausa language			
8	Do the students attach pride to their course of study?			
9	Do the students disclose their course of study to students studying other courses?			
10	Do you think majority of the students consider other courses more honorable than their own?			
11	Do you think the students consider teachers/lecturers of other courses more honorable than teachers/lecturers of Hausa language?			
12	Do you think the students have been bold enough to stand for and/or depend Hausa language as a course whenever it is challenged?			
13	Do you think the students would like to be named after the course, (i.e. Malam Hausa, Bahausha, DanHausa etc)?			
14	Do you think the students have been advising others to study Hausa language?			
	C: Students' attitudes towards learning Hausa language			
15	Do the students enjoy the nature of Hausa language as their course of study?			
16	Were majority of the students happy (specifically about the course), when they got admission to study Hausa language?			
17	Do you think the attitudes of the students towards the course have been the cause of their lack of interest on some educational activities?			

18	Do the students participate fully, and willingly, in continuous assessments of Hausa language?			
19	Do the students attend conferences, seminars or public lectures on Hausa language?			
	D: Students' Preference of Hausa Language as Life Career			
20	Do you think many of the students will further their education on Hausa after the first degree?			
21	Under normal circumstances (i.e. favorable salary), do you think majority of the students will like it if they have to teach Hausa language as their career?			
22	Do you think many of the students have vision of helping towards the development of the language?			
23	Are the students attempting to enrich Hausa literature by writing books for publication?			

Appendices

Appendix 1: List of Lecturers of the Department of Nigerian Languages, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

S/NO	STAFF NAMES	AREA OF SPECIALIZATION
1.	AMFANI Ahmed Halliru	Linguistics
2.	ABDULLAHI Haruna Birniwa	Literature
3.	BUNZA Aliyu Muhammad	Culture
4.	YAHAYA Abdullahi Bayero	Literature
5.	YAKASAI Salisu Ahmad	Language
6.	MALUMFASHI Ibrahim Aliyu	Literature
7.	A. B. Yahaya	Literature
8.	IBRAHIM Ahmad Mukoshy	Language
9.	DUNFAWA Atiku Ahmed	Literature
10.	DANTUMBISHI Muhammad Abdulhameed	Language
11.	USMAN Bello Bala	Literature
12.	ABDULLAHI Ibrahim S/Sudan	Culture
13.	ABDULLAHI Isah Muhammad	Language
14.	UMAR Sama'ila	Language
15.	BUNZA Dano Balarabe	Literature
16.	MUSA Shehu	Culture
17.	MUHAMMAD Mustapha Umar	Language
18.	IDRIS Yahaya	Literature
19.	IBRAHIM Nazir Abbas	Language
20.	AMINU Nasiru	Culture

21.	GOBIR Yakubu Aliyu	Culture
22.	BUNZA Umar Aliyu	Literature
23.	YALWA Lawan Danladi	Linguistics
24.	ABDULLAHI Sarkin Gulbi	Culture
25.	RABAN Aliyu Rambo	Culture
26.	ABDULBASIR Ahmad Atuwu	Literature

Appendix 2: List of 100L Students of the Department of Nigerian Languages, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (2015/2016 session)

Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

THE MOST PEACEFUL UNIVERSITY IN NIGERIA

LIST OF STUDENTS THAT REGISTERED FOR A PROGRAM

Program: Bachelor of Arts Hausa

Session: 2015/2016

Level: 100

Serial/No	Admission Number	Full Names
1	1510106001	Bello, Mustapha
2	1510106002	Attahiru, Ummu Usman
3	1510106003	Yusuf , Amiru Muhammad
4	1510106004	Yahaya, Mubarakatu Sakanau
5	1510106005	Musa, Mukhtar
6	1510106006	Abdullahi, Aminu
7	1510106007	Maude, Aminu
8	1510106008	Aliyu, Faruku Gwandu
9	1510106009	Umar, Adamu
10	1510106010	Umar, Hadiza Goronyo
11	1510106011	Garba, Idris
12	1510106012	Hamma'ali, Kamilu Bello
13	1510106013	Ibrahim, Alhaji
14	1510106014	Yakubu, Shukurana
15	1510106016	Umar, Lawal Bafashi
16	1510106017	Umar, Usman
17	1510106018	Aliyu, Zara'u
18	1510106019	Kunchi, Saduku Uba
19	1510106020	Jibril, Mubarak
20	1510106021	Haruna, Suleiman Dogondaji
21	1510106022	Ibrahim, Aliyu
22	1510106023	Isah, Usman
23	1510106024	Galadima, Hussaini
24	1510106027	Ahmad, Isah

Appendix 3: List of 200L Students of the Department of Nigerian Languages, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (2015/2016 session)

Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

THE MOST PEACEFUL UNIVERSITY IN NIGERIA

LIST OF STUDENTS THAT REGISTERED FOR A PROGRAM

Program: Bachelor of Arts Hausa

Session: 2015/2016

Level: 200

Serial/No	Admission Number	Full Names
1	1410106001	Lawal, Zubairu Ibrahim
2	1410106002	Abdullahi, Murtala Gwiwa
3	1410106003	Shehu, Umar Alhaji
4	1410106004	Abubakar, Hussaini
5	1410106007	Abdulkadir, Bello Aliero
6	1410106008	Maccido, Abubakar
7	1410106009	Uwaisu, Muttaka Sulaiman
8	1410106010	Umar, Bilyaminu Tureta
9	1410106011	Abdullahi, Musa
10	1410106013	Umar, Samir
11	1410106015	Labaran, Abdullahi
12	1410106016	Abdulsalam, Abubakar
13	1410106017	Abdullahi, Hussaini Idris
14	1410106018	Musa, Abubakar Sabo
15	1410106021	Umar, Mardiyya
16	1410106022	Murtala, Mubarak
17	1410106028	Kabir, Firdausi Tafida
18	1520106015	Suleiman, Imrana
19	1520106025	Abubakar, Lukman Altine

Appendix 4: List of 300L Students of the Department of Nigerian Languages, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (2015/2017 session)

Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

THE MOST PEACEFUL UNIVERSITY IN NIGERIA

LIST OF STUDENTS THAT REGISTERED FOR A PROGRAM

Program: Bachelor of Arts Hausa

Session: 2015/2016

Level: 300

Serial/No	Admission Number	Full Names
1	1210106001	Ibrahim, Hamisu Yusuf
2	1210106002	Abubakar, Zaharadeen Mainiyo
3	1210106003	Salihu, Kudu Mohammad
4	1210106004	Ahmad, Hassan
5	1210106007	Umar, Harisu
6	1210106008	Adam, Usman Rogo
7	1210106009	Ladan, Muazu
8	1210106010	Hirabri, Shehu
9	1210106011	Isyaku, Sulaiman
10	1210106012	Umar, Muhammad Bello
11	1210106013	Danu, Mukhtar Garba
12	1210106014	Suleiman, Mansur
13	1210106015	Arzika, Shamsu Awashaka
14	1210106016	Muhammad, Malami Yabo
15	1210106017	Umar, Buhari Wali
16	1210106018	Ibrahim, Nuhu Bayawa
17	1210106021	Abubakar , Samira Wali
18	1210106023	Abubakar, Yahaya
19	1210106025	Mustapha, Anas
20	1210106026	Balarabe, Bello Mohammed
21	1210106027	Saleh, Zaharadeen
22	1210106034	Iliyasu, Usman
23	1210106037	Buhari, Mansur Ubandawaki
24	1210106038	Buhari, Fauziya Abdullahi

25	1210106041	Lawal, Ibrahim S Fawa
26	1210106043	Muhammad, Fatima Umar
27	1210106044	Alkali, Naziru Muhammad
28	1210106045	Abdulkadir, Mainasara
29	1210106047	Umar, Hassan
30	1310106001	Musa, Ado Magaji
31	1310106003	Musa, Abbas
32	1310106004	Aliyu, Abubakar
33	1310106006	Abdullahi, Mu'awuya Kamba
34	1310106007	Sani, Junaidu
35	1310106008	Hamidu, Yusuf
36	1310106014	Abubakar, Umar Kalgo
37	1310106016	Aliyu, Usman
38	1310106018	Abdullahi, Usman
39	1310106019	Abubakar, Aminu
40	1310106020	Shehu, Aliyu
41	1310106021	Umar, Shamsu
42	1310106023	Bello, Aminu
43	1310106025	Musa, Ashiru
44	1310106027	Abdurrahaman, Abdulbasid Muhammad
45	1310106028	Idris, Yusuf
46	1310106029	Mustapha, Aliyu
47	1310106031	Isah, Auwal
48	1310106032	Bisco, Sanusi Ibrahim
49	1310106035	Alkasim, Musa Lukman
50	1310106038	Bala, Aminu
51	1310106042	Murtala, Shuaibu Abdullahi
52	1310106044	Bello, Abdul-mumini
53	1310106045	Balarabe, Mansur
54	1310106048	Abubakar, Saratu
55	1310106052	Muhammad, Bello
56	1310106053	Usman, Iliyasu Maru
57	1420106020	Musa, Bature Musa
58	1420106025	Musa, Usamatu
59	1420106032	Muhammad, Mikail

Appendix 5: List of 400L Students of the Department of Nigerian Languages, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (2015/2016 session)

Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

THE MOST PEACEFUL UNIVERSITY IN NIGERIA

LIST OF STUDENTS THAT REGISTERED FOR A PROGRAM

Program: Bachelor of Arts Hausa

Session: 2015/2016

Level: 400

Serial/No	Admission Number	Full Names
1	1011106001	Habibu, Balarabe Sifawa
2	1011106008	Ja`afar, Sanusi Bashir
3	1011106009	Sadiq, Maryam Yelwa
4	1011106016	Garba, Nuraddeen
5	1011106018	Yari, Chika
6	1011106019	Abubakar, Muhammed
7	1011106020	Bello, Faruk
8	1011106021	Shamsuddeen, Bello Hamma`ali
9	1011106023	Ibrahim, Zaki
10	1011106034	Musa, Almustapha
11	1011106036	Mande, Maryam Shagari
12	1011106037	Nasiru, Abdullahi Sifsws
13	1011106038	Magaji, Abdullahi
14	1011106039	Shuaibu, Muhammad
15	1011106047	Namadi, Maryam Rabiu
16	1011106050	Shuaibu, Nasir Ambursa
17	1011106053	Suleiman, Saddam Maye
18	1011106059	Saadu, Zainab Moriki
19	1011106060	Ibrahim, Aminu Muh`d
20	1011106061	Ibrahim, Mudassiru
21	1011106063	Umar, Sani
22	1011106065	Umar, Abdullahi
23	1110106001	Garba, Ahmad
24	1110106015	Isah, Nasiru

25	1110106017	Haruna, Yusuf Arume
26	1110106029	Isah, Rahama Funtua
27	1110106031	Umar, Dargaza Bello
28	1110106038	Rabiu, Nura
29	1110106050	Suleiman , Jamila
30	1110106057	Sani, Yusuf Gulma
31	1110106096	Dalhatu, Umaima Yartsakuwa
32	1110106098	Bello, Aisha
33	1110106105	Shehu, Balkisu
34	1110106115	Musa, Sanusi
35	1110106116	Sahabi, Abdullahi Kalgo
36	1110106117	Umar, Hafsatu Muhammad
37	1110106118	Danjumma, Samira Muhammad
38	1110106129	Usman, Ashiru Gabasawa
39	1110106134	Abubakar, Zayyanu Shuni
40	1110106155	Abubakar, Nuhu Dalhat
41	1110106171	Samaila, Saifullahi
42	1110106185	Shehu , Habibu Alhaji
43	1110106194	Bara'u, Halliru
44	1110106198	Garba, Hussaini Takardawa
45	1110106200	Balarabe, Babangida
46	1110106202	Lawal, Sulaiman
47	1110106243	Bello, Abdulnasir
48	1110106257	Usman, Junaidu
49	1110106276	Labaran, Sadisu
50	1110106278	Shehu, Kabiru
51	1110106287	Muhammad, Umar Balle
52	1110106300	Umar, Nafisa
53	1110106302	Bello, Attahiru Sahabi
54	1110106333	Murtala, Nasiru
55	1110106349	Abubakar, Sani
56	1110106381	Aliyu, Farida
57	1110106382	Abdullahi, Manir
58	1110106388	Tanko, Tukur Muhammad
59	1110106406	Bawa, Jamilu Mungadi
60	1110106409	Muhammad, Jafaru
61	1110106410	Ja'afaru , Sambo
62	1110106420	Bello, Idris

63	1110106430	Ahmed, Lawal
64	1110106437	Moyi, Bello Mohammed
65	1110106438	Suleiman, Bello
66	1110106447	Kasim, Mustapha Abdullahi
67	1110106457	Labbo, Tijjani Alhaji
68	1110106478	Saidu, Murtala Shehu
69	1110106489	Haruna, Muhammad
70	1110106516	Maccido, Ibrahim Sanyinna
71	1110106532	Ladan, Babangida Dundaye
72	1110106577	Ibrahim, Mustapha
73	1110106588	Umar, Sadiq
74	1110106596	Umar, Bello Gwiwa
75	1110106609	Aliyu, Ibrahim
76	1110106682	Gandi, Sa'idu Ibrahim
77	1110106683	Attahiru, Basira Koko
78	1110106692	Maidamma, Abubakar
79	1110106697	Lawali, Murtala
80	1110106699	Atiku, Asmau Garba
81	1110106712	Yahaya, Jamilu Bawa
82	1110106729	Abdul-razak, Sirajo
83	1110106739	Suleman, Aliyu
84	1110106832	Umar, Aminu Kalgo
85	1220106006	Musa, Abubakar
86	1220106020	Dayi, Rilwanu
87	1220106022	Maryam, Yakubu Yeldu
88	1220106039	Abdullahi, Ahmed Gada
89	1320106005	Ladan, Zayyanu
90	1320106009	Akilu, Usman Koko
91	1320106010	Shehu, Nura
92	1320106011	Akilu, Abbas Koko
93	1320106012	Salihu, Abdullahi
94	1320106022	Magaji, Ukashatu
95	1320106040	Ahmad, Hussaini
96	1320106043	Muhammad, Muslim